

STUDYING THE LIFE AND CREATION OF MUHAMMAD YUSUF ON THE
BASIS OF PROBLEM EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article written about Life and work of Muhammad Yusuf, examples of literary works and their analysis and as well studying the life and creation of Muhammad Yusuf on the basis of problem education.

Key words: Life and work, literary works, analysis, creation, poems

In today's democratic and independent state of Uzbekistan, issues of national spirit, spirituality and enlightenment are one of the most priority directions of state policy. Cultural, educational and artistic evenings are held in cultural centers, higher educational institutions, academic lyceums and secondary vocational colleges and general secondary schools. In this country, attention is paid to the spiritual growth of every person. Because a spiritual person can understand the dreams and desires of the Uzbek people and try to realize them.

Spirituality is a force that has been passing from century to century, influencing the mind and spirit of people. Therefore, educating a spiritual person is one of the most urgent problems of today. If we can raise spiritual people among our youth today, we will establish a strong foundation for our future tomorrow. According to the requirements of today's educational programs, poetry and prose works written in the spirit of patriotism, together with folk oral works, play an important role in increasing the spiritual wealth of young people.

In such works, the important problems of today are reflected, and they encourage readers to agree with the times. And he can find a solution to the problems raised in the works or express his opinions.

In today's process of globalization and integration, raising a spiritual and mature person is the main issue of our society. Therefore, it is the duty of every pedagogue to acquaint young people with works inspired by the spirit of national patriotism.

Uzbek literature is so beautiful that we can find various flowers and colors in its garden. In this Boston, a generation of charming poets, who are not alike and do not repeat each other, grows up again and again.

One of such unique poets is undoubtedly the national poet of Uzbekistan, the beloved son of our people, Muhammad Yusuf.

Muhammad Yusuf was born on April 26, 1954 in the village of Qovunchi, Marhamat (Mingtepa, where the famous Dukchi Eshan uprising took place in 1898) district of Andijan region in an ordinary family. In this village, he spent his innocent childhood and joyful adolescence.

*Nechun qulluq qilmay Andijonga men —
Shu yurtda tug`ildim, shu yurtda o`sdim.
Agar do`stim bo`lsa, bitta u do`stim —
Nechun qulluq qilmay Andijonga men!..*

*Yodimga o`t tushsin, etmasam yodlar —
Dukchi eshonlari qilgay faryodlar.
Uni tavof etgan Mashrabdek zotlar,
Nechun qulluq qilmay Andijonga men, —*

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After receiving high school education, Muhammad Yusuf entered the Institute of Russian Language and Literature in Tashkent and graduated in 1978. Samples of his first poems were published in 1976 in the pages of the "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan" weekly.

At that time, Uzbek poetry reached a new level of growth, a unique creative competition between many talents such as Shavkat Rahman, Usman Azim, Khurshid Davron, etc. It was not an easy task to boldly enter this circle of creativity and occupy a suitable place. Muhammad Yusuf was one of the poets who succeeded in this task and drew the attention of the literary public to his side.

In 1978-1980, the young artist worked in the "Book Lovers" society of the republic, in 1980-1986 in the capital's "Tashkent Akshomi" newspaper, and in 1986-1992 in the Literary and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Gulam. The years of working in this publishing house played an important role in the creative destiny of Muhammad Yusuf. After all, at that time, Erkin Vahidov, one of the greatest artists of his time, was in charge of this dargah, and the spirit of creativity that prevailed in all departments gave a serious impetus to the development of the young poet.

Muhammad Yusuf tried hard to prove himself as a poet among his pen pals and teachers who created memorable works in various directions of poetry:

Shoir shunday ko`pki, ularga yer tor,

Hammasi mashhur va hammasi nomdor,

Ulug`vor, ularga yetmoq ko`p dushvor.

Ammo ular oyga bosib yuzini

Turganda osmonin bag`riga ilk bor

Biz olib borgaymiz tuproq isini,

Gulday dimog`iga tutamiz, qizim,

Biz hali hammadan o`tamiz, qizim!..

In 1992-1995, Muhammad Yusuf worked in the newspaper "Voice of Uzbekistan" and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan (UzA). Since 1997, the poet has been appointed deputy chairman of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan.

Although his poems were often published in periodicals, his first poetry collection was published relatively late - in 1985. After that, the poet wrote «Bulbulga bir gapim bor» (1987), «Iltijo» (1988), «Uyqudagi qiz» (1989), «Halima enam allalari» (1989), «Ishq kemasi» (1990), «Ko`nglimda bir yor» (1990), «Bevafo ko`p ekan» (1991), «Yolg`onchi yor», «Erka kiyik» (1992), «Osmonimga olib ketaman» the league has arrived. He also turned to major poetic genres and created epics such as «Osmonning oxiri» and «Qora quyosh».

The independence of our country opened new horizons in Muhammad Yusuf's work. His beautiful poems in honor of the nation and the country's independence echoed in the hearts of millions with their sincerity, simplicity, and artistic excellence. Dozens of the poet's poems such as «Vatanim», «Xalq bo`l, elim», «Dunyo», «Inshoolloh», «O`zbekmomo», «Iqror»,

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«Tilak» are real poetry, how to sing the country. There have been works that have proved the necessity.

Muhammad Yusuf was awarded the title of "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" in 1998 for his high creative achievements during the years of independence.

Muhammad Yusuf's work occupies an important place in the development of Uzbek singing in the next period. From the greatest and most talented representatives of our national art to amateur singers, poet's poems are set to tunes, and even now, poet's poems are read with love and sung to newly composed tunes. The main source of works of late singer Muhyiddin Khalikov, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Ozodbek Nazarbekov, Yulduz Usmanova, People's Artist of Uzbekistan G`iyos Boytoyev is related to the poems of Muhammad Yusuf.

Unfortunately, Muhammad Yusuf's life was short. He died of a heart attack on July 31, 2001, during a creative trip to Ellikkala district of Karakalpakstan, while reciting poetry in front of hundreds of fans. Just like Babur and Shaukat Rahman, Muhammad Yusuf lived only 47 years.

However, this life was enough for a charming poet to be born, to grow up, to serve the country and nation that brought him up and leave a good name behind him.

*Ol, deya bir Egam, osmonga uchsa ruhlarim,
Bir ajib moviy diyor bo`ynini quchsa ruhlarim,
Ko`k mening ko`ksim bo`lur, yulduzlari - anduhlarim,
Gul o`pib, gul yopinib har dilda mozorim qolur,
Men ketarman bir kuni, navolarim, zorim qolur...*

We know well from history lessons that the Uzbek nation is one of the oldest nations in the world. And this nation experienced unprecedented events in history. It is located between two rivers, the land is fertile, the people are hardworking, and there is no one who has not admired this land, which has created unique examples of sedentary culture. Invaders came from every corner and tried to rob this beautiful country - to steal its wealth and enslave its people.

Our nation survived all the tests like a samandar (a legendary bird that was born in the fire and survived the fire) and came out with honor. However, these struggles, aspirations for freedom, of course, did not pass without victims and losses. The national values, the original children of the nation, who knew the freedom of the country above all else, died on these battlefields.

There are several advantages of studying the life and work of Muhammad Yusuf on the basis of problem-based learning. Through this method, students' ability to analyze works of art will be increased. In fact, the main goal of creating problem-based education is the ability to think independently at a high level. If the educational process teaches the student to think independently, then it can be considered as a learning-cognitive process based on the development of education.

The problem situation is carried out in the following stages:

Along with the work of Muhammad Yusuf, we can use the method of problem-based education to study his life.

In this, a problematic question about the life of Muhammad Yusuf is thrown among the students.

For example:

a) A problematic situation is created:

Could Muhammad Yusuf have written such beautiful works if he had not been born in Marhamat district of Andijan?

b) The problematic situation is based on:

Muhammad Yusuf was born in 1954 in Marhamat district of Andijan region in a simple family.

c) The problem situation is analyzed together with the students:

Muhammad Yusuf's life and work can be studied in different ways.

d) There are several ways to solve the problem situation:

All places of Uzbekistan are peaceful and beautiful. Fergana region is very beautiful. The mountains, hills, and people of this land are also special.

e) A solution to the problematic situation is found:

No, Muhammad Yusuf would not have been able to write such wonderful poems if he had not been born in Andijan.

During this period, a number of soirs were noticed in Uzbek literature, almost all of them shone like bright stars in the sky of literature. Among these shining stars is Muhammad Yusuf, whose rains are still lighting up the sky of our literature. His immortal poems and epics written about homeland, love, love, mother, and life will not leave people's minds for a long time, they will remain in the depths of their hearts.

Muhammad Yusuf sang true love. He wrapped it in all kinds of silent words - he did not hide it, but he composed it in a poem, and he absorbed his heartache in these poems. We can understand the poet's heartaches through his poems and poetic epics such as "Mehr qolur" "Vatanim", "Surat", "Osmonning oxiri", "Qora quyosh".

The life of a writer is interesting and rich. And his creations taste the worlds. The variety and color of the themes in his poems show that Muhammad Yusuf is a prolific artist.

In order to study the poet's life and work, we should use not only one problematic method of education, but several other methods.

Such methods include "Brainstorming" method, "Decision Tree" method, and "Cluster" method.

Although Muhammad Yusuf is not among us today, he lives in our hearts through his works. There is a proverb in our people – it is not the life that people have lived, but what they have done that determines their life. Even though Muhammad Yusuf lived such a short life, he wrote works lasting for centuries and took a deep place in the hearts of the Uzbek people. His poems are currently being translated into other languages of the world: English, French, German, Russian.

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